

EFFECT OF MATRIX RIVETTING IN WOVEN FABRIC HOLES TO INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: Matrix rivetting formed in woven fabric holes of woven fabric-reinforced composite laminates is proposed. The geometry of fabric holes is analysed and a method for calculating the matrix rivetting area is established. In order to know the effect of interlaminar matrix rivetting to delamination resistibility, the relation between matrix rivetting area and interlaminar fracture (G_{1c} and G_{2c}) is studied. Glass-fiber plain woven fabrics with eight different warp and filling densities are adopted to reinforce epoxy resin. The experimental results indicate that interlaminar fracture toughness will evidently increase with the increasement of matrix rivetting area. It is suggested that weaves with relative low warp or filling densities should be used to improve delamination growth resistibility of woven fabric-reinforced composite laminates when adhesion strength between fibers and matrices is low and delamination occurred easily.

KEYWORDS: matrix rivetting, woven fabric hole, interlaminar fracture toughness

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, woven fabric composite laminates are widely used in technical practice, especially in the field of aerospace, marine and sports technology. This is because of their favorable mechanical properties and low fabrication cost. Then, interplyer delamination is considered the most critical failure mode limiting the long-term fatigue life of certain composite laminates [1]. Previous studies in this area have been largely concerned in improving fiber-matrix adhesion strength and using three-dimensional woven fabric and great effects had been obtained in improving delamination growth resistance. But, for example, cost and fabrication, to a certain extent, their application have been limited. By a great amount observation of delamination surface of fabric composite laminates we find that one part of matrix is peeled from the fiber surface and the other part in fabric holes is matrix fracture. Therefore, we propose that interlayers are combined by bonding between fibers and matrices and matrix rivettings formed in fabric holes. Vandeurzen and Naik analysed the effect of the yarn undulation to performance of woven fabric composites [2-4]. However, the influence of woven fabric holes is neglected. In order to know the effect of interlaminar matrix rivetting to interlaminar fracture energy, two commonly used tests DCB (Double-Cantilever Bean) and ENF (End-Notched Flexure) are adopted. Glass-fiber plain weaves with eight different warp and filling densities are adopted to reinforce epoxy resin. A three-dimensional analytical

model is presented to analyse the geometric characteristics of fabric holes to obtain matrix rivetting area.

RIVETTING AREA OF WOVEN FABRIC HOLES

The shape of matrix rivetting in woven fabric hole is determined by hole's space shape. Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the hole's geometric characteristics before we calculate the rivetting area. The space shape of woven-fabric hole is not a simple cuboid as imagination. In fact, it is very complicated. Generally, the hole's cross section is similar to rectangle with relatively small acute angle as Figure.1(b) shows. The shape and size of cross section will change with different position. The area of cross section is smallest in hole's center and it will expand with the increasement of the distance between section position and center. Considering fracture principle, we define the smallest cross section area as rivetting area. To facilitate the analytical model of fabric hole we assume: 1) the cross section shape of warp and filling is track-round, as Fig.1(a) shows; 2) the spatial curve of warp and filling in interlacing points circuncircle; 3) woven fabric structure phase is 5.0 [5].

Figure 1: Analytical mode of woven fabric hole

According to geometric symmetry of woven fabric hole, based on above assumption, matrix rivetting area A_r can be obtained by:

$$A_r = A_{LONM} - 4(A_{OBD} + A_{OPQ}) \tag{1}$$

where A_{LONM} is the rectangle area of LONM, A_{OBD} and A_{OPQ} represent the area of curve-side triangle OBD and OPQ. A_{LONM} can be calculated by warp and filling densities and yarns' width and thickness. However, the calculation of A_{OBD} and A_{OPQ} is relatively complicated. So, a three-dimensional analytical model is established. By projective geometrical analysis of cross section, the curve equation of curve OB can be expressed by:

$$Y(x) = r_f \sqrt{1 - \left[\frac{\sqrt{R_f^2 - x^2} - (R_f - r_f)}{\sqrt{R_f^2 - x^2} - \sqrt{(R_f - r_f)^2 - x^2}} \right]^2} \quad (2)$$

where R_f is the curve-radius of filling in interlacing point, $2r_f$ is the thickness of filling. Therefore, A_{OBD} can be calculated by:

$$A_{OBD} = \int_0^{\delta_w/2 + \gamma_w} Y(x) dx \quad (3)$$

where δ_w is the distance among warps, $2r_w$ is the thickness of warp. In the same way, A_{OPQ} can be obtained. Now, we introduce a rivetting area corrected coefficient K_r :

$$K_r = \frac{A_r}{A_{HIJK}} \quad (4)$$

where A_{HIJK} is the projective area of woven fabric hole. So, the percentage of rivetting area of unit woven fabric area P_r (%) can be calculated by:

$$P_r (\%) = K_r [1 - E (\%)] \quad (5)$$

where E(%) is the percentage of yarn projective area of unit woven fabric area. Figure.2 shows a SEM micrograph of glass-fiber plain woven fabric for reinforcement. The relevant parameters of glass-fiber plain woven fabrics with different warp and filling densities are listed in Table 1.

Figure 2: A SEM micrograph of plain woven fabric

Table 1: Relevant parameters of glass-fiber plain woven fabric

Number of Glass-Fiber Plain Woven Fabric	Densities of Warp and Filling (Ends and Picks/cm)		Kr (%)	E (%)	Pr (%)
1	20	22	1.279	93.75	7.99
2	20	20	1.257	92.51	9.34
3	20	16	1.236	90.23	12.07
4	20	12	1.219	87.89	15.13
5	14	14	1.328	95.68	5.74
6	14	12	1.292	93.79	8.02
7	14	10	1.273	91.91	10.30
8	14	8	1.259	89.86	12.77

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

Glass-fiber plain woven fabrics with different structure parameters (different rivetting area) are used to reinforce epoxy. Consolidation agent is triethylene amine.

Interlaminar Fracture Toughness Testing

In general, interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates are determined by interlaminar fracture energy. A number of test methods have been developed to measure the interlaminar fracture energy of composite laminates [6]. The interlaminar fracture energy, measured in term of the strain energy release rate, is defined as the amount of strain energy released in propagating delamination by a unit length. In this experimental, two commonly used interlaminar fracture toughness test methods of the double-cantilever beam (DCB) test and the end-notched flexure (ENF) test are adopted to measure the strain energy release rate G_{1c} and G_{2c} under mode I loading and mode II loading. The specimens for both DCB test and ENF test are rectangular beams $300 \times 12 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ cut from laminates $(0^\circ / 0^\circ / 45^\circ / -45^\circ / 90^\circ)_s$. Initial delamination are formed by PBTP film (thickness $50 \mu\text{m}$) embedded in the mid-place of the laminates. The unit crack length of propagating delamination is 10mm. The test are carried out on an Instron 1185 universal testing machine at a cross-head speed of 2mm/min [7]. In DCB test, optical microscope is used to observe crack initiation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the variation of interlaminar fracture toughness with percentage of matrix rivetting area Pr(%). With the increasement of Pr(%), the values of both G_{1c} and G_{2c} will increase evidently. Under the condition of a certain warp density, the reduction of fiber volume fraction 5~10% (by reducing filling density 10~20%) will obtain the improvement of

interlaminar fracture toughness 50~100%. We consider the main reason is that the woven fabrics with relative low warp or filling densities have more rivetting area and more matrix rivetting will formed in interlayers, so more fracture energy is needed in propagating delamination. Generally, tensile or shear fracture energy of per unit matrix area is larger than the energy of interface peeling between matrix and fiber. The delamination surface of both DCB and ENF specimens were analysed with scanning electron microscope. Figure 4 shows four SEM micrographs of the gold coated delamination fracture surfaces. At lower magnification (a) and (b), shows the existence of matrix rivetting in woven fabric holes and the fracture cross section shape of matrix rivetting. At higher magnification (c) and (d), shows that matrices are peeled from the yarn surface. Observations indicate that delamination fracture associates with the fracture of matrix rivetting and the failure of fiber/matrix interface.

CONCLUSIONS

The test results indicated that matrices will form matrix rivetting in woven fabric holes of woven fabric-reinforced composite laminates and their influences upon interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates are very evident. This research provided a convenient and effective method to improve the interlaminar fracture toughness of woven fabric-reinforced composite laminates by structure design of woven fabric. It is suggested that woven fabrics with relative low warp or filling densities should be adopted to improve delamination resistibility of composite laminates when adhesion strength between fibers and matrices is low and delamination failure often occurs.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thanks are due to faculty of Textile Material Lab of Northwest Institute of Textile Science and Technology. Further thanks are addressed to Yiou KeXun who kindly supplied the testing materials.

(a) Warp densities: 20 Ends/cm

(a) Warp densities: 14 Ends/s

Figure 3: Variation of interlaminar fracture toughness with percentage of matrix rivetting area P_r (%)

Figure 4: Micrograph of delamination surface of woven fabric reinforced composite laminates. SEM magnifications:(a),(b) 30 x; (c),(d) 500 x.

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